

included in the 1990 DS analysis because of damage.

Means and ranges for the S₁ lines are presented in Tables 1 and 2. Lines comparable with or better than the best check occurred in both seasons, although this population had not undergone previous selection for yield.

In 1989 WS, correlations between S₁ and the corresponding S₃ lines were significant for all traits except adjusted yield. Yield of IR68 was reduced by typhoon damage.

In 1990 DS, correlations were significant for all traits except days to 50% flowering and percentage unfilled grains.

As S₁ lines are segregating for male sterility, and the amount of seed is limited, it is difficult to evaluate yield directly. Our study indicates that yield components and grain quality traits can be measured on fertile S₁ plants in small plots. These measurements appear to reflect differences observed in fertile S₁-derived S₃ or S₄ lines. This indicates S₁ selection could be used in a recurrent selection program to improve these traits. ■

Table 1. Ranges, means, and LSD for grain quality and agronomic traits of 46 S₁ lines with check means and correlation coefficients (r) between the S₁ and the corresponding S₃ generations. IRRI, 1989 WS.

Character	S ₁ lines		Checks		LSD (0.05)	r ^a
	Range	Mean	IR36	IR68		
Plant height (cm)	91-170	120	96	128	10.9	0.92**
Days to 50% flowering	91-125	105	89	103	7.3	0.68**
Brown rice length (mm)	6.0-7.4	6.7	6.7	7.9	0.41	0.82**
Brown rice shape (L/W)	2.35-3.60	3.07	3.45	3.70	0.31	0.90**
Gelatinization temp score	3.71-7.00	5.74	4.46	6.50	1.13	0.70**
Panicles/hill	10-20	15	20	13	5.5	0.49*
Spikelet no./panicle	92-206	151	120	131	46.5	0.77**
% unfilled grains	19-55	36	23	45	16.3	0.58**
100-grain weight (g)	2.18-3.16	2.56	2.35	3.02	0.28	0.60**
Adjusted yield (g/2.25m ²)	537-1414	965	848	749	452	0.26 ns

^aCorrelation between 26 pairs of S₁ and their derived S₃ lines. *, ** = significant at the 5 and 1% level, respectively. ns = nonsignificant.

Table 2. Ranges, means, and LSD for grain quality and agronomic traits of 32 S₁ lines with check means and correlation coefficients (r) between the S₁ and the corresponding S₄ generations. IRRI, 1990 DS.

Character	S ₁ lines		Check	LSD (0.05)	r ^a
	Range	Mean	IR36		
Plant height (cm)	84-150	108	109	10.1	0.68**
Days to 50% flowering	83-102	93	95	4.7	0.36 ns
Brown rice length (mm)	6.0-7.6	6.8	8.1	0.43	0.80**
Brown rice shape (L/W)	2.30-3.45	2.93	3.60	0.29	0.81**
Gelatinization temp score	4.13-7.00	6.09	6.84	1.27	0.64**
Panicles/hill	12-23	16	14	4.3	0.58**
Spikelet no./panicle	105-229	164	197	39	0.69**
% unfilled grains	9-26	15	14	10.2	0.25 ns
100-grain weight (g)	2.07-2.84	2.41	2.63	0.28	0.61**
Adjusted yield (g/2.25 m ²)	955-1893	1331	1690	460	0.47*

^aCorrelation between 26 pairs of S₁ and their derived S₄ lines. *, ** = significant at the 5 and 1% level, respectively. ns = nonsignificant.

Estimates of combining ability of some rice varieties in diallel crossing systems

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We studied the nature of genetic control and amount of heterosis available for spikelets per panicle and identified suitable donors for this character.

The rice genotypes crossed in a complete diallel set were IR8 (IRRI), IR8423 (IRRI), 415 (INSA), IR19746-11-33 (IRRI), VX1-2 (USSR), X1 (INSA), CICA7 (IRRI), Tam den HP (INSA), VE19, and Te hat to.

The 90 F₁ cross combinations and their parents were grown in a randomized block design with three replications in winter-spring 1986-87. Ten competitive randomly selected plants from each replication were analyzed.

Highly significant F ratios for general combining ability (GCA), specific combining ability (SCA), and reciprocal effects (Table 1) indicate difference among these effects. The GCA effects of each parent given in Table 2 indicate that IR8423-132-6-22, IR19746-11-33, and Tam den HP are good general combiners for number of spikelets/panicle.

For spikelets per panicle, the variances due to GCA were higher than those due to SCA for IR8423-132-6-22, X1, VE19, and Te hat to. This indicates the role of additive gene action was predominant in inheritance of the trait. In all entries

except X1, VE19, and Te hat to, nonadditive gene action was predominant in controlling this character. ■

Table 2. Estimate of GCA effects for spikelets/panicle.^a

Parent	GCA effects (gi)	Parent	GCA effects (gi)
IR8	5.57	x1	6.18
IR8423-132-6-22	12.75	CICA7	-8.54
415	-16.01	Tam den HP	10.65
IR19746-11-33	9.34	VE19	-9.69
VX1-2	6.54	Te hat to	-16.81

^aStandard error: gi - gj = 0.35 (i ≠ j).

Table 1. Analysis of variance of combining ability.

Source of variance ^a	Sum of squares	DF	Mean square	Value	F-table P = 0.05
GCA	18908.00	9	2100.89	2122.11	2.53
SCA	11646.34	35	332.75	336.12	1.83
RE	6137.50	45	136.39	137.77	1.56
Error	0.99	171			

^aGCA = general combining ability, SCA = specific combining ability, RE = reciprocal effect.